

Questions to entrepreneurs to help them share their entrepreneurial stories

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Preamble

Initial set of questions developed as part of the TG Entrepreneurship of the European Robotics Forum, co-developed by researchers, practitioners and entrepreneurs.

The set was adapted, elaborated and tested in several sessions and also as part of the MedTechs course offered by the Institute for Biomedical Informatics at the University Hospital Cologne and the Medical Faculty of the University of Cologne.

The set of questions is open for improvements and additions.

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The questions

1. When did you start thinking of creating your own company? Was it during your university studies?
2. Can you please share your background (education and previous experience)?
3. What made you launch an enterprise?
4. Did you have any formal education on entrepreneurship?
5. What did you wish would have known at the start, that you know now, and that you would like to share?
6. What is your greatest success so far?
7. Which were the biggest challenges you had to overcome to achieve this success ?
8. What you consider as your biggest loss? How could you have avoided them ?
9. What are the key elements in launching and running a start-up successfully?
10. What is your key advice for new/budding entrepreneurs?
11. Did you have any mentors?
12. What was the trigger to go ahead?
13. How do you assess the current market situation and your competition?

14. What has been your experience of funders: as investors, business angels, corporate, venture?
15. How did you get your first funding?
16. What do you think the most difficult thing has been about starting and running your own company?
17. What do you wish you had known when you first set up your company?